

Mooring Data Report

for the

Processes driving Exchange at Cape Hatteras (PEACH) program

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INTRODUCTION

The Processes driving Exchange At Cape Hatteras (PEACH) project aims to identify the processes that control the exchange of waters between the shelves along the eastern seaboard of the US and the open ocean. By design, PEACH focuses on the shelf waters that flow southward from the Middle Atlantic Bight (MAB) and northward from the Southern Atlantic Bight (SAB) that converge near Diamond Shoals. Furthermore, at the core of the PEACH program, MAB and SAB shelf waters interact with the Gulf Stream and Shelf Break Front resulting in large net exchanges to and from the open sea. The PEACH project includes remote sensing and in situ observations—including radars, moored platforms and gliders (Figure 1)—as well as a numerical modeling component, to fully address these processes.

Figure 1. PEACH array off of Cape Hatteras showing moored instruments, glider tracks, radar coverage and other regional observations.

This report focuses on the moored aspects of PEACH. It describes the data processing, quality control, and graphical products of velocity profiles, water temperature and salinity, and meteorological data

from moorings gathered during the PEACH field phase. The moored results provide early insight into the movement of different water masses throughout the PEACH array in context with seasonal variations and several storm events.

Time-series of velocity profiles and water properties are collected using upward-looking acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs) and conductivity, temperature, and depth (CTD) sensors mounted on bottom frames and trawl-resistant bottom pods. Each of the two PEACH meteorological moorings consists of a surface buoy instrumented with meteorological sensors (wind speed and direction, air temperature, humidity and barometric pressure, downwelled short- and long-wave radiation, and still images), satellite communications (Iridium), near surface and mid-depth CTDs.

An additional moored asset utilized in PEACH is from the Renewable Ocean Energy Program (ROEP). As part of ROEP, a multi-year, time-series of ADCP and CTD data (2013 to present) collected at approximately 35.14N, 75.11W at the Ocean Energy (OE) site (Figure 1) provides an important long-term record of currents and water masses prior to and during PEACH. The deployment at the OE site has been maintained and serviced by researchers at the Coastal Studies Institute (CSI) and collaboratively extended for the PEACH project.

Finally, data resources available through the National Buoy Data Center (NDBC) provide critical surface observations. Wind and wave data from NDBC 44014, 41025, 41064, 41159 and 44095 provide additional atmospheric observations and valuable surface conditions at Cape Hatteras and input from the SAB and MAB. The buoys at 41025 and 44014 are owned and maintained by NDBC, and the waverider at 44095 is owned and maintained by CSI. The collocated buoy and waverider in Onslow Bay at 41064 and 41159 are owned and operated by UNC-W Coastal Ocean Research and Monitoring Program (CORMP).

This report is a visual catalog of ADCP, CTD, and meteorological data collected during 20+ months of the PEACH field program. By using consistent graphical elements, key features can be identified easily and associated with other data parameters or other locations. In addition, it provides an initial look at data quality and return to identify where further work is needed. This report is organized as follows. First, mooring locations and time spans of deployment, turnarounds, and recovery are outlined. Second, the folder organization and descriptions of the various graphical products are provided. Plots in these folders were generated from the level1 dataset. Finally, details of processing buoy, ADCP, and CTD data are provided including initial quality control (QC) and cleanup steps taken to arrive at level1.

MOORINGS

The bottom frames/pods and surface buoys of the PEACH array (Table 1) were deployed during the AR-

15 cruise aboard the *R/V Neil Armstrong* (operated by WHOI) in April 2017 (Andres, et al., 2017). Figure 2 shows the locations of the shelf moorings (B1, B2, A4, and A7) and the shelf-break moorings (A1, A2, A3, A6, and A8) along with the NDBC buoys and the OE site at A5 (A5OE).

During *R/V Neil Armstrong* turn-around cruise AR-26 (January 8-21, 2018) and small boat operations aboard the *R/V Caroline* (operated by CSI), throughout Spring and Summer 2018, bottom frames (B1, B2, A4, and A7), pods (A1, A2, and A3) and buoys (B1 and B2) were recovered (Table 1) and redeployed. Data from the ADCPs and CTDs were downloaded, and batteries refreshed (or sensors swapped out). Then, the frames, pods and buoys were returned to service on location.

Finally, during the *R/V Neil Armstrong* recovery cruise AR-33 (November 17-27, 2018), bottom pods (A1, A2, A3, and A8) and buoys (B1 and B2) were recovered (Table 1). Further ship operations aboard *R/V Caroline* were required to dive for bottom frames B1/A4 (March 3, 2019) and B1/A7 (July 1, 2019). *M/V Tiki* trawled unsuccessfully for pods at A5OE and A6 that were located but not recoverable on AR-33. Further salvage operations are being considered to attempt recovery of A5OE and A6.

UPDATE: July 30, 2021 -- A5OE washed up in Bermuda in May, 2021 and was recovered. The CTD recorded during 2017-2018 while deployed in position. On Dec 01, 2018, it left the bottom (shortly after AR-26 was completed) and drifted until it washed ashore. A6 was found and recovered by WHOI ROV dive on June 01, 2021.

This report summarizes the results obtained from these ADCPs and CTDs in context with the meteorological, wave, and upper CTD data collected at PEACH buoys (B1 and B2) and additional buoys and waveriders operated by NDBC, CSI, and CORMP.

Figure 2. Map of PEACH moorings where ADCP and CTD sensors are placed.

Table 1. Deployment and recovery details for each mooring and each deployment. The sources of locations, deployment and recovery times are from the AR-15 cruise report (Andres, et al., 2017), AR-15, AR-26 and AR-33 cruise E-logs and field notes.

		Latitude	Longitude	Water Depth	Deployed (UTC)	Recovered (UTC)
B1 buoy	deploy1	35 46.692 N (35.77820)	075 5.682 W (-75.09470)	36 m	2017-04-19 16:00	2018-01-10 14:00
	deploy2	35 46.692 N (35.77820)	075 5.548 W (-75.09247)	36 m	2018-01-10 20:15	2018-11-19 22:00
B2 buoy	deploy1	34 46.938 N (34.78230)	075 56.472 W (-75.94120)	30 m	2017-04-20 14:36	2018-01-16 13:30
	deploy2	34 46.938 N (34.78230)	075 56.472 W (-75.94120)	30 m	2018-01-16 21:00	2018-11-22 05:00
B1 frame	deploy1	35 46.776 N (35.77960)	075 5.574 W (-75.09290)	36 m	2017-04-19 18:00	2018-01-10 20:00
	deploy2	35 46.781 N (35.77968)	075 5.564 W (-75.09274)	36 m	2018-01-14 17:00	2019-03-08 15:00
B2 frame	deploy1	34 46.832 N (34.78053)	075 56.509 W (-75.94182)	30 m	2017-04-20 17:00	2018-01-16 13:00
	deploy2	34 46.832 N (34.78054)	075 56.505 W (-75.94176)	30 m	2018-01-17 00:00	2019-07-01 12:00:00
A4 frame	deploy1	35 25.765 N (35.42942)	075 14.870 W (-75.24783)	30 m	2017-05-09 14:21	2017-11-01 15:21
	deploy2	35 25.707 N (35.42845)	075 14.920 W (-75.24867)	30 m	2017-11-01 19:00	2018-06-22 20:00
	deploy3	35 25.034 N (35.41723)	075 15.226 W (-75.25377)	30 m	2018-06-08 16:00	2019-03-08 14:00
A7 frame	deploy1	35 0.001 N (35.00002)	075 40.578 W (-75.67630)	30 m	2017-05-10 16:00	2017-11-02 12:00
	deploy2	34 59.975 N (34.99958)	075 40.644 W (-75.67740)	30 m	2017-11-02 18:30	2018-08-06 18:00
	deploy3	(34.99913)	(-75.6777)	30 m	2018-08-06 18:00	2019-07-01 12:00:00
A1 pod	deploy1	36 0.038 N (36.00063)	074 50.027 W (-74.83378)	99 m	2017-04-18 13:21	2018-01-11 16:21
	deploy2	36 0.036 N (36.00061)	074 50.033 W (-74.83389)	100 m	2018-01-17 22:18	2018-11-23 21:10
A2 pod	deploy1	35 45.082 N	074 51.799 W	95 m	2017-04-18	2018-01-11

		(35.75137)	(-74.86332)		16:27	14:31
	deploy2	35 45.108 N (35.75180)	074 51.797 W (-74.86328)	96 m	2018-01-17 20:00	2018-11-23 18:40
A3 pod	deploy1	35 35.700 N (35.59500)	074 48.528 W (-74.80880)	98 m	2017-04-18 19:00	2018-01-11 12:50
	deploy2	35 35.724 N (35.59540)	074 48.528 W (-74.80880)	96 m	2018-01-17 18:09	2018-11-19 20:10
A6 pod	deploy1	34 56.532 N (34.94220)	075 18.462 W (-75.30770)	236 m	2017-04-22 13:07	2021-06-01 10:30
A8 pod	deploy1	34 33.935 N (34.56558)	075 40.556 W (-75.67593)	230 m	2017-04-21 15:38	2018-11-22 12:45
A5OE pod	deploy5	35 8.243 N (35.13738)	075 5.641 W (-75.09402)	283 m	2016-12-04 16:00	2017-06-02 15:00
	deploy6	35 7.170 N (35.11950)	075 6.741 W (-75.11235)	236 m	2017-06-13 00:00	2021-05-01 00:00*
41025 buoy	deployall	35 0.317 N (35.00528)	075 24.200 W (-75.40333)	64 m	2003-03-28 00:00	2018-12-21 07:00
44095 buoy	deployall	35 45.000 N (35.75000)	075 19.800 W (-75.33000)	18 m	2012-04-09 00:00	present
44014 buoy	deployall	36 36.634 N (36.61056)	074 50.600 W (-74.84333)	45 m	1990-10-01 00:00	present

* A5OE deploy6 -- Washed ashore on Bermuda Island, May 2021.

** A6 deployall was found and recovered by ROV Jason (WHOI) on June 01, 2021.

GRAPH PRODUCTS AND FOLDERS

Graphs are accessible at the following shared Google Folder link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wfpz4OtyiaO6vYcfWkklYrPKkhvud0Jc?usp=sharing>.

Graphs generated from level1 dataset are subdivided into two main categories, summary and by month. While summary plots give an overview of data by buoy, adcp, ctd and temperature-salinity (TS) diagram, plots by month provide further detail at each mooring. Because most instruments were turned around once or twice, graphs are further identified by their deployment number. By maintaining the graphs as individual images with consistent graph ranges, an image viewer such as Preview in Google Drive can be utilized to page through the graphics in each of the folders or to open multiple web browser tabs between folders. The following list describes each folder of graphs.

summary_buoy -- stacked time series plots of

B1, B2 -- wind, surface air temp, upper and mid-depth water temp, and short- and long-wave radiation data

41025, 44014, 41064 -- wind, surface air temp, surface water temp, and wave data

44095, 41159 -- surface water temp, and wave data

summary_adcp -- stacked time series with depth of current magnitude, vertical velocity (w), backscatter, and average correlation magnitude, percent good, and error velocity. Also provided is a stacked time series of ADCP health parameters with pitch, roll, heading, water temperature, and pressure.

summary_ctd -- stacked time series plots of water temperature, salinity, and density for each deployment.

summary_TS -- temperature-salinity (TS) plots for each ctd colored by month.

bymonth_b1 -- buoy, adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_b2 -- buoy, adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_a4 -- adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_a7 -- adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_a1 -- adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_a2 -- adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_a3 -- adcp, ctd (by month)

bymonth_ndbc41025 -- buoy (by month)

bymonth_ndbc44095 -- buoy (by month)

bymonth_ndbc44014 -- buoy (by month)

DATA PROCESSING

Because of the different sensor types and platforms, data are canonically processed by platform (buoy, frame, pod) and packages (met, wind, ADCP, CTD).

Storing and processing data is done by levels. Level0 is the raw data downloaded directly from the instrument. For all instruments processed, the original data are converted to scientific values but in vendor formats that require special programs or knowledge to extract. It is assumed that each sensor was calibrated pre-deployment and configured for depth, duration and sampling frequency appropriate for the deployment. Whatever the original data format, hex, binary, netCDF or ascii, the data are parsed and read using MATLAB, and then stored into easily-used and consistent, MATLAB format.

Level1 data have been trimmed, quality controlled and, where obvious, gross offsets adjusted but still maintain the original sampling interval. Each deployment is processed and documented individually. Specific steps to processing each type to level1 data are summarized below. QC thresholds, and additional notes for specific issues for each mooring and deployment are also listed. PEACH level1 data are “bad flagged” by setting the value to Not-a-Number (NaN) in the data set if it exceeds a certain threshold or fails the QC test, while data in level0 keeps the original value(s).

Level2 data take level1 data for each package and each deployment and hourly average each parameter so all data are on the same timebase. Further the individual deployments of given a platform (A1, A2, etc) and package (CTD, ADCP) are stitched together. The specific steps to processing each type from level1 to level2 are summarized below.

BUOY Processing

(level0)

1. Store NDBC ascii data available from <http://www.ndbc.noaa.gov/>.
2. Retrieve netCDF data, for B1 and B2 from <http://whewell.marine.unc.edu/data/peach/>
3. Convert netCDF and parse ascii data to MATLAB format.
4. Trim start and end of data time series to deployment and recovery times listed in Table 1, except NDBC data.

(level1)

1. Compared wdir at B1 and B2 with nearest neighbor and adjusted sensor offsets.
2. Used range test and time-continuity tests to QC meteorological data to eliminate (bad flag) observations in time and also set manually for known sensor malfunction. NDBC data already quality controlled.
3. Combined best wspd, wgust, wdir from two anemometers to provide most complete record of wind at each buoy B1 and B2.
4. Computed air temperature proxy from internal canister temp for when air temp sensor malfunctioned for B1 only. B2 had an almost complete air temp record.

(level2)

1. NDBC, B1 and B2 buoy data were combined from level1 data and averaged hourly. While NDBC buoy data contains wave, upper water temperature, we pulled wave height, wave period, near-surface water velocity, and surface water temperature variables from ADCP and CTD (level1 data) for B1 and B2 for downstream bulk heat flux calculations.

Table of range test tolerances of B1 and B2 met data

Wind speed	$0 \leq \text{wspd} \leq 75$ (m s ⁻¹)
Wind direction	$0 < \text{wdir} \leq 360$ (degrees)
Air Pressure	$100 < \text{press} < 2000$ (mbar)
Infrared Radiation	$100 < \text{pir} < 540$ (W m ⁻²)

Table of time-continuity test tolerances of B1 and B2 met data, if $t(i)-t(i-1) < 3$ hrs

Wind speed	$ \text{wspd}(i) - \text{wspd}(i-1) < 20$ (m s ⁻¹)
Air Temperature	$ \text{atemp}(i) - \text{atemp}(i-1) < 3$ (deg C)
Air Pressure	$ \text{press}(i) - \text{press}(i-1) < 5$ (mbar)
Infrared Radiation	$ \text{pir}(i) - \text{pir}(i-1) < 50$ (W m ⁻²)

ADCP Processing

(level0)

1. Store of original raw binary data.
2. Convert raw binary data to MATLAB format.

(level1)

3. Trim start and end of data time series to deployment and recovery times listed in Table 1.
4. Correct gross time offsets.
5. QC tests of ADCP data to eliminate (bad flag) observations in time and depth that are of poor quality following, Haines, et al., 2011, IOOS, 2015 and Symonds, 2006.
Tests include general sensor health, horizontal and vertical velocity range, echo intensity, correlation magnitude, percent good, error velocity, and surface masking and are listed in Table 2 with tolerances used. Cumulative bad flags for sensor health and signal quality are applied to all profile parameters.
6. Check ADCP magnetic variation (adcp_mvar) used in instrument to compute velocity components relative to true north is same as magnetic variation for the site in platform database (platform_mvar). If not the same (adcp_mvar not equal to platform_adcp) and adcp_mvar = 0, then rotate north and east components by platform_mvar. If not the same (adcp_mvar not equal to platform_adcp) and adcp_mvar > 0, the north- and east-velocity component data are rotated back to magnetic north by adcp_mvar and then rotated using platform_mvar.
7. Backscatter (dB) derived from echo intensity and operating frequency.

(level2)

1. Hourly average each deployment ADCP from level1 and compute depth averaged currents.
2. Interpolate 2D fields to common platform depth (where z=0 is mean sea level -/DOWN) so the next step can happen
3. Stitch together multiple ADCP deployments for a given mooring location.
4. Compute depth-averaged horizontal currents. Detide depth-averaged using utide.

Table 2. QC tests and hierarchy, with tolerances used for PEACH ADCP data. Data are set to NaN if value tested exceeds specified tolerance(s).

Test	Tolerance
Sensor Health Tests (for each sample time)	
ADCP Error Status Bit	1
Change in Tilt (Pitch and Roll), Heading	tilt>5 deg, heading>45 deg
Temperature	<0 or >40 deg C
Salinity	<30 or >40 psu
Signal Quality Checks (for each sample time and profile bin)	
Change in Echo Intensity	> 80 counts
Correlation Magnitude	< 90 counts

Percent Good	< 50 %
Surface Mask Fraction. If have pressure record compute water depth (WD). Since beam angle is 20 deg, $\cos(20) \approx 0.94$ is fraction to keep of WD profile, the anything above last 0.06 is masked of each profile.	0.06
Velocity Checks (for each sample time and profile bin)	
Magnitude of Velocity	> 3 m/s
Vertical Velocity	> 0.5 m/s
Error Velocity	> 0.35 m/s

Table 3. Specific ADCP issues encountered by mooring location and deployment.

Site	Deploy	Issue -- Resolution
A1, A2, A3	deploy1 deploy2	No pressure sensor -- used pressure from collocated CTD in pod for depth and surface masking.
A1	deploy2	Overall tilt 15-20 deg ($\cos(15+20) \approx 0.82$) -- used surface mask fraction 0.18
A2	deploy2	Time offset of ADCP temperature relative to CTD temperature -- Best correlation by shifting ADCP time to -4.7 hours. Checked that CTD press correlated well with nearby CTD pressures to verify the CTD was not offset.
A3	deploy2	Pod moved downslope significantly from 94 m to 108m depth. Luckily, ADCP was configured with enough bins to still reach surface -- no changes needed as surface masking algorithm based on Surface Mask Fraction handles this case.
A4	deploy2	Pressure sensor failed, no other pressure since CT Only -- surface mask based on range at which change in Echo Intensity (> 90 counts).
A6	deployall	
A8	deployall	Overall tilt 10 deg ($\cos(10+20) \approx 0.87$) -- used surface mask fraction 0.13

CTD Processing

(level0)

1. Store of original hex data.
2. Convert raw hex data to MATLAB format.

(level1)

3. Trim start and end of data time series to deployment and recovery times listed in the table.
4. Correct gross time offsets.
5. Used gross range tests (Table 4) to quality control CTD data to eliminate (bad flag) observations in time that are out-of-range and suspicious following IOOS, 2016.
6. Analyze and apply obvious offsets in conductivity on case-by-case basis reported in Table 5. Sucking in debris or bubble into a conductivity cell is number one cause of offsets. If offset or linear fit is not obvious or correctable by comparison to nearby sensor (e.g. temperature on ADCP at same locations), then considered bad.
7. Salinity and density re-derived after all bad flagging done.

(level2)

1. Hourly average each deployment CTD from level1
2. Stitch together multiple CTD deployments for a given mooring location. (If on a bottom frame it will be labeled "ctd", but if upper, middle and bottom at a mooring like the buoy locations, then labeled "ctd1", "ctd2" and "ctd3", respectively.

Table 4. QC tests with tolerances used for PEACH ADCP data. Data are set to NaN if value tested exceeds specified tolerance(s).

Test	Tolerance
Temperature	<-5 or >35 deg C
Conductivity	<3 or >6 S/m
Pressure	A4,A7,B1,B2 (>40 dbar), A1,A2,A3 (>150 dbar), A5OE (>290) A8 (>260)

Table 5. Specific CTD issues encountered by mooring location and deployment.

Site	Deploy	Issue -- Resolution
A1, A2, A3	deploy1 deploy2	No pump. Multiple salinity spikes with strong front passage -- NEEDS TO BE ADDRESSED.
A2	deploy2	Cond shift starting at March 4, 2018 at 04:00 UTC until end of deploy -- Offset of 0.170 applied to cond between these dates.
A4	deploy1	Time offset of CTD pressure relative to co-located ADCP pressure. -- Best correlation by shifting CTD time by +3.80 hours. Checked that ADCP pressure correlated well with nearby pressure records to verify the ADCP was not offset. Bad cond cell determined at post-project calibration -- bad flag whole record

A4	deploy2	<p>Pod was deeply buried in sediment on recovery. See Gabe's notes and pictures. Temperature record compared with ADCP temperature show on March 07, 2018 after 10:00UTC, CTD temp lagged ADCP temp and not varying as much. -- Bad flag temp from this date and time until recovery of deploy2.</p> <p>Bad cond cell determined at post-project calibration -- bad flag whole record</p>
A4	deploy3	<p>Temp</p> <p>Bad cond cell determined at post-project calibration -- bad flag whole record</p>
A7	deploy1	<p>Time offset of CTD pressure relative to co-located ADCP pressure. -- Best correlation by shifting CTD time by +3.75 hours. Checked that ADCP pressure correlated well with nearby pressure records to verify the ADCP was not offset.</p> <p>Bad cond cell determined at post-project calibration -- bad flag whole record</p>
A7	deploy2	No Data!! Sensor did not record -- no cond, temp or press.
A7	deploy3	Bad cond cell determined at post-project calibration -- bad flag whole record
B1 -- ctd3	deploy1	<p>Cond shift between Aug 28, 2017 and Oct 6, 2017 -- Linear offset from 0.3590 and 0.3900 applied to cond between these dates.</p> <p>CTD off the frame in the sand when divers recovered -- cond bad flagged after time when depth increases around Oct 15, 2017 by ~0.5 m</p>
B1 -- ctd3	deploy2	<p>Same CTD redeployed (no spare), pump not working, temp and cond working. Two periods of cond shift in the record were corrected by offsets.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Jan 17, 2018 to May 19, 2018 -- Because we have ctd1 and ctd2, and ctd3 temp is good, we could identify period of well-mixed water and hence what ctd3 cond should be and what the offset is. Fitting a polynomial yy (cond_offset) vs xx (datenum), we corrected the ctd3 cond between these dates. The polynomial coeff is decreasing powers are $P = [-0.0067 \ 0.0119 \ 0.0540 \ 0.0529 \ 0.0638]$, where $P(1)*X^N + P(2)*X^{(N-1)} + \dots + P(N)*X + P(N+1)$ and $N=4$. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Aug 1, 2018 to Dec 10, 2018 -- Linearly increasing offset applied.

		<p>The effect of the two corrections are plotted here.</p>
B2 -- ctd1	deploy1	Cond looks bad for Nov 29-Dec 07, 2017 -- Cond bad flagged for this time period
B2 -- ctd3	deploy1	~20 cond spikes -- Cond bad flagged manually for each case
A6 -- ctd	deployall	<p>Temp compared with ADCP temperature lags and responds less starting June 03, 2020. Recovery video footage with ROV Jason, pilots had to shake the pod to release sediment holding it down. Suspect the CTD was buried. -- Temp bad flagged for June 03, 2020 until recovery on June 01, 2021.</p> <p>A few (2) cond spikes before March 04, 2018 -- removed by bad flagging.</p> <p>The data show salinity to become nearly constant and not varying starting with the storm event of early March 2018 and persisted to the end. We think the storm caused the cond cell to become clogged with sediment. -- Cond bad flagged from March 04, 2018 until recovery.</p>

SUMMARY PLOTS

The summary plots below provide a “gut check” that all timing issues between different sensors (ctd and adcp) and deployments were time-based correctly by comparing the pressure records from each. Since the field area is fairly small we can assume all sensors would experience the roughly same tidal cycles offshore. If there was any mismatch, it was usually the result of incorrect time set upon configuration (e.g. local time set instead of GMT). These offsets in time were addressed for level1. Offsets in pressure (y-axis) resulted from the different mounting locations on the platform and changes in pressure as a platform becomes buried in the sand.

Temperature differences between ctd and adcp at the same location resulted from ctd being buried in the sand or sensor failure. Between mooring locations, correlation of temperature variability provided confidence that temperature sensors were functioning and QC'd appropriately for the level1 dataset.

Salinity plots show correlation between different mooring locations and provide confidence that conductivity and temperature were functioning and QC'd appropriately for the level1 dataset.

ADCP and CTD pressure

ADCP and CTD Bottom Temperature

CTD Salinity

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